

Presidential Reference of 2025 as a Judicial Reinterpretation of Constitutional Design : An Analysis

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Abstract

The Presidential Reference of 2025 under Article 143 of the Indian Constitution marked a significant moment in the judicial-executive dialogue on constitutional interpretation. Unlike earlier advisory opinions, this reference was not confined to clarifying narrow legal questions but touched upon the very design of constitutional governance, particularly the balance between state autonomy, gubernatorial discretion, and the supervisory role of the Union. The Supreme Court's advisory opinion effectively reinterpreted foundational principles of federalism, democratic accountability, and constitutional morality. By doing so, the Court reaffirmed its role as the guardian of the Constitution while simultaneously redrawing the contours of institutional powers. This paper demonstrates how advisory opinions, though technically non-binding, have become an instrument of constitutional evolution in India. The 2025 reference thus stands as a judicial reinterpretation of constitutional design, with long-term implications for the relationship between constitutional organs, cooperative federalism, and the preservation of democratic values.

Keywords

Advisory Opinion, Constitution, Federalism, Governor, Secularism.

Introduction

The advisory opinion in India, enshrined in Article 143[1] of the Constitution, rests on the idea that the Supreme Court, as the guardian of the Constitution, should guide the executive on complex questions of law or fact of public importance. Such opinions are non-binding and meant only to aid the President in decision-making, preserving the separation of powers. Since the commencement of the Constitution, the Supreme Court has treated references with the seriousness of contentious cases, inviting detailed arguments and delivering reasoned judgments. Beginning from the Delhi Laws Act Reference, 1951,[2] to till date, advisory opinions have gone beyond mere advice, shaping the interpretation of federalism, fundamental rights, natural resource allocation, and executive discretion. While advisory opinions are constitutionally optional for the government, they have carried significant persuasive authority, often functioning as instruments of judicial reinterpretation and constitutional evolution in India. The history of advisory jurisdiction in India shows its dual role, a tool for constitutional clarity and a mechanism for judicial reinterpretation of constitutional design.

Objective of study

This paper demonstrates how advisory opinions, though technically non-binding, have become an instrument of constitutional evolution in India. The 2025 reference thus stands as a judicial reinterpretation of constitutional design, with long-term implications for the relationship between constitutional organs, cooperative federalism, and the preservation of democratic values.

Review of Literature

Background of Presidential Reference 2025

On April 8, 2025, a two-judge bench comprising Justices J.B. Pardiwala and R. Mahadevan delivered a landmark ruling in *State of Tamil Nadu v. Governor of Tamil Nadu*. [3] The Supreme Court emphatically rejected the notion of an "absolute" or "pocket veto" by the Governor and clarified that such unfettered discretion undermines the constitutional fabric of democratic governance. The Court outlined the three constitutionally permissible actions under Article 200[4] of the Indian Constitution: (i) grant assent to a bill, (ii) withhold assent and return it to the legislature with a message, or (iii) reserve the bill for the President's consideration. Crucially, once the legislature re-passes a bill, even without any changes, the Governor is bound to grant assent and cannot reserve it for the President. To curb undue delays, the Supreme Court prescribed enforceable timelines for gubernatorial action: (a) when withholding assent or reserving a bill, the decision must be made within one month; (b) when withholding assent contrary to the advice of the Council of Ministers, the action must be taken within three months; and (c) assent to bills re-passed by the state legislature must be granted within one month. In this case, the Court found that Governor R.N. Ravi had unduly delayed assent to ten bills passed by the Tamil Nadu legislature. Invoking Article 142,[5] which empowers the Court to ensure "complete justice," it deemed the bills to have received assent, thereby bringing the prolonged constitutional stalemate to an end. Moreover, the Court emphasized that if a bill is reserved by the Governor on the grounds of unconstitutionality, the President ought to seek the Supreme Court's advisory opinion

under Article 143,[6] thereby reinforcing the Court's role in safeguarding constitutional values.

Main Text

Fourteen questions of Presidential reference 2025[7]

President Droupadi Murmu referred to the Supreme Court in her May 13, 2025 Presidential Reference under Article 143(1)[8] of the Constitution of India. These focus on clarifying constitutional powers and judicial limits concerning Governors and the President, especially in light of the April 8, 2025 Tamil Nadu Governor judgment. The Presidential Reference of 2025 placed before the Supreme Court a series of intricate constitutional questions. It asked what options are constitutionally available to a Governor under Article 200[9] when a Bill is presented for assent, and whether the Governor is bound by the aid and advice of the Council of Ministers in exercising those options. It further questioned whether the Governor's discretion under Article 200[10] is justiciable, or whether Article 361[11] creates an absolute bar to judicial review of such actions. Another issue was whether, in the absence of an expressly prescribed timeline, the judiciary can impose timelines or prescribe the manner of exercising powers under Article 200,[12] and correspondingly, whether the President's discretion under Article 201[13] is justiciable and subject to judicially imposed timelines. The reference also asked whether the President is required to seek the Supreme Court's opinion under Article 143[14] when a Bill is reserved by the Governor, and whether the decisions of the Governor and President under Articles 200[15] and 201[16] are open to judicial scrutiny before a Bill becomes law. It raised doubts over whether the Court, by invoking Article 142,[17] can substitute its own directions for the constitutional powers of the Governor or President, and whether a Bill passed by the State Legislature without the Governor's assent can be treated as a law in force under Article 200.[18] The President also sought clarity on whether, under the proviso to Article 145(3),[19] the Court must first determine if a matter involves a substantial question of constitutional interpretation before referring it to a larger bench. Another query was whether the Court's powers under Article 142[20] are confined to procedural matters or whether they extend to issuing directions inconsistent with constitutional or statutory provisions. Finally, the reference asked whether, apart from the jurisdiction under Article 131,[21] the Constitution permits the Supreme Court to adjudicate disputes between the Union and the States.

Why Presidential reference 2025 is unique

Under the Indian Constitution, it is solely the privilege of the President of India to decide which issues should be referred to the Supreme Court and which should not. The Supreme Court, however, has the power to determine whether or not to answer the questions so referred. The advisory opinion mechanism has a significant advantage over judicial review, particularly with respect to the element of time. While the advisory procedure operates at the stage when a mechanism for testing the validity of statutes is immediately required, judicial review often comes into play long after the need has arisen and, for practical purposes, sometimes not at all. Since judicial review depends on private initiative to challenge the validity of a law, and on common law requirements of locus standi or adequate interest, the ordinary process of judicial review is often inadequate to meet the real needs of the public. For the first time, the President has sought an advisory opinion on a judgment of the Supreme Court itself. Essentially, this reference questions whether the Supreme Court has the power to limit the authority of the Governor and the President under Articles 200[22] and 201[23] of the Indian Constitution. Although the Constitution is silent about the discretionary powers under these provisions, various judgments and the Constituent Assembly debates have attempted to define the limits of Union authority and the scope of gubernatorial discretion. The nature of the Presidential Reference of 2025 raises the question of why the Union Government chose to invoke Article 143[24] to challenge the judgment in the Tamil Nadu Governor case. The present government, holding 240 seats in the Lok Sabha, is a minority government largely dependent on regional political parties. It is tough take positions against the principle of federalism, especially because many provisions of the judgment promote state autonomy and democratic space for regional parties. As the Union Government relies heavily on its coalition partners, particularly strong regional parties that dominate their respective states, it cannot afford to act against their interests. Consequently, the Central Government opted for a middle path by seeking clarity from the Supreme Court through the 14 questions posed in the 2025 Presidential Reference.

How this reference is judicial reinterpretation of constitutional design

The Presidential Reference of 2025 appears to be a judicial reinterpretation of constitutional design in a broader sense. Most of the questions raised in this reference have already been addressed in various judgments of the Supreme Court and were also elaborately discussed during the Constituent Assembly debates. However, whether to answer these questions, and to what extent, lies solely within the discretion of the Supreme Court. At the same time, several questions in this reference seem puzzling, since the Constitution of India itself provides elaborate explanations on many of these issues. Moreover, in relation to the reference questions, it appears that certain constitutional provisions are in tension with one another. The Indian Constitution is founded on federal principles, and state governments are equally accountable to the people. If laws passed by state legislatures fail to take effect because of prolonged delays by Governors in granting assent, it undermines the functioning of federal

democracy. In such a scenario, if the Constitution itself prescribes no time limit, one may legitimately ask how the Supreme Court can impose a binding time limit on the President. It is a well-established principle that the Governor and the President must exercise their discretion in accordance with the demands of the time and constitutional morality. Hence, to raise a question as to whether the discretionary powers of the Governor or the President are justiciable seems misplaced, as the matter has already been clarified in constitutional practice and judicial precedent.

Conclusion

The questions raised in the Presidential Reference of 2025 suggest that the President may have taken an inappropriate route to examine the constitutionality of the Tamil Nadu Governor case judgment. A large number of these questions already have clear answers in previous Supreme Court judgments and in the constitutional text itself. However, it also appears that the outcome of this reference is likely to reinforce and strengthen earlier rulings concerning the Articles mentioned in the reference. Ultimately, it remains the duty of the Supreme Court of India to safeguard the Constitution, uphold federalism, and protect the democratic principles of the country. The outcome of this reference will be highly decisive for the future of Union–State relations in India.

References

1. *Power of President to consult Supreme Court (1) If at any time it appears to the President that a question of law or fact has arisen, or is likely to arise, which is of such a nature and of such public importance that it is expedient to obtain the opinion of the Supreme Court upon it, he may refer the question to that Court for consideration and the Court may, after such hearing as it thinks fit, report to the President its opinion thereon (2) The President may, notwithstanding anything in the proviso to Article 131, refer a dispute of the kind mentioned in the said proviso to the Supreme Court for opinion and the Supreme Court shall, after such hearing as it thinks fit, report to the President its opinion thereon. Constitution of India, art143.*
2. *Delhi Laws Act, 1951 (AIR 1951 SC 322).*
3. *2025 (INSC) 481.*
4. *Assent to Bills. When a Bill has been passed by the Legislative Assembly of a State or, in the case of a State having a Legislative Council, has been passed by both Houses of the Legislature of the State, it shall be presented to the Governor and the Governor shall declare either that he assents to the Bill or that he withholds assent therefrom or that he reserves the Bill for the consideration of the President: *Provided that the Governor may, as soon as possible after the presentation to him of the Bill for assent, return the Bill if it is not a Money Bill together with a message requesting that the House or Houses will reconsider the Bill or any specified provisions thereof and, in particular, will consider the desirability of introducing any such amendments as he may recommend in his message and, when a Bill is so returned, the . House or Houses shall reconsider the Bill accordingly, and if the Bill is passed again by the House or Houses with or without amendment and presented to the Governor for assent, the Governor shall not withhold assent therefrom: * Provided further that the Governor shall not assent to, but shall reserve for the consideration of the President, any Bill which in the opinion of the Governor would, if it became law, so derogate from the powers of the High Court as to endanger the position which that Court is by this Constitution designed to fill. Constitution of India, art. 200.*
5. *Enforcement of decrees and orders of Supreme Court and orders as to discovery, etc. (1) The Supreme Court in the exercise of its jurisdiction may pass such decree or make such order as is necessary for doing complete justice in any cause or matter pending before it, and any decree so passed or order so made shall be enforceable throughout the territory of India in such manner as may be prescribed by or under any law made by Parliament and, until provision in that behalf is so made, in such manner as the President may by order prescribe. (2) Subject to the provisions of any law made in this behalf by Parliament, the Supreme Court shall, as respects the whole of the territory of India, have all and every power to make any order for the purpose of securing the attendance of any person, the discovery or production of any documents, or the investigation or punishment of any contempt of itself. Constitution of India, art. 200.*
6. *Supra note 1.*
7. *1. What are the constitutional options before a Governor when a Bill is presented to him under Article 200 of the Constitution of India? 2. Is the Governor bound by the aid & advice of the Council of Ministers while exercising all options available under Article 200? 3. Is the exercise of constitutional discretion by the Governor under Article 200 justiciable? 4. Is Article 361 an absolute bar to judicial review of actions taken by a Governor under Article 200? 5. In the absence of a constitutionally prescribed timeline, can judicial orders impose timelines and prescribe the manner of exercise for all powers under Article 200 by the Governor? 6. Is the exercise of constitutional discretion by the President under Article 201 justiciable? 7. In the absence of a constitutionally prescribed timeline,*

can judicial orders impose timelines and prescribe the manner of exercise for the President under Article 201? 8. Is the President required to seek the Supreme Court's opinion under Article 143 when the Governor reserves a Bill for the President's assent or otherwise? 9. Are the decisions of the Governor and President under Articles 200 and 201 justiciable prior to a law coming into force? Is judicial adjudication over the content of a Bill permissible before it becomes law? 10. Can the Supreme Court, under Article 142, substitute the constitutional powers or orders of the President or Governor? 11. Is a law made by the State Legislature considered a law in force without the Governor's assent under Article 200? 12. In view of the proviso to Article 145(3), must the Court first determine whether a question involves a "substantial question of law as to interpretation of the Constitution" before referring it to a bench of at least five judges? 13. Are the powers under Article 142 limited to procedural matters, or do they extend to issuing directions or orders that are contrary to, or inconsistent with, existing substantive or procedural provisions of the Constitution or other laws? 14. Does the Constitution bar any other jurisdiction of the Supreme Court to resolve disputes between the Union and State Governments, apart from a suit under Article 131? Presidential Reference 1 of 2025.

8. *Supra* note 1.

9. *Supra* note 4.

10. *Ibid*.

11. *Protection of President and Governors and Rajpramukhs.* (1) The President, or the Governor or Rajpramukh of a State, shall not be answerable to any court for the exercise and performance of the powers and duties of his office or for any act done or purporting to be done by him in the exercise and performance of those powers and duties: Provided that the conduct of the President may be brought under review by any court, tribunal or body appointed or designated by either House of Parliament for the investigation of a charge under article 61: Provided further that nothing in this clause shall be construed as restricting the right of any person to bring appropriate proceedings against the Government of India or the Government of a State. (2) No criminal proceedings whatsoever shall be instituted or continued against the President, or the Governor of a State, in any court during his term of office. (3) No process for the arrest or imprisonment of the President, or the Governor of a State, shall issue from any court during his term of office. (4) No civil proceedings in which relief is claimed against the President, or the Governor of a State, shall be instituted during his term of office in any court in respect of any act done or purporting to be done by him in his personal capacity, whether before or after he entered upon his office as President, or as Governor of such State, until the expiration of two months next after notice in writing has been delivered to the President or the Governor, as the case may be, or left at his office stating the nature of the proceedings, the cause of action therefor, the name, description and place of residence of the party by whom such proceedings are to be instituted and the relief which he claims. Constitution of India, art. 361.

12. *Supra* note 4.

13. *Bills reserved for consideration.* When a Bill is reserved by a Governor for the consideration of the President, the President shall declare either that he assents to the Bill or that he withholds assent therefrom: Provided that, where the Bill is not a Money Bill, the President may direct the Governor to return the Bill to the House or, as the case may be, the Houses of the Legislature of the State together with such a message as it mentioned in the first proviso to article 200 and, when a Bill is so returned, the House or Houses shall reconsider it accordingly within a period of six months from the date of receipt of such message and, if it is again passed by the House or Houses with or without amendment, it shall be presented again to the President for his consideration. Constitution of India, art. 201.

14. *Supra* note 1.

15. *Supra* note 4.

16. *Supra* note 13.

17. *Supra* note 5.

18. *Supra* note 4.

19. *Rules of court, etc..* The minimum number of Judges who are to sit for the purpose of deciding any case involving a substantial question of law as to the interpretation of this Constitution or for the purpose of hearing any reference under article 143 shall be five: Provided that, where the Court hearing an appeal under any of the provisions of this Chapter other than article 132 consists of less than five Judges and in the course of the hearing of the appeal the Court is satisfied that the appeal involves a substantial question of law as to the interpretation of this Constitution the determination of which is necessary for the disposal of the appeal, such Court shall refer the question for opinion to a Court constituted as required by this clause for the purpose of deciding any case involving such a question and shall on receipt

of the opinion dispose of the appeal in conformity with such opinion. Constitution of India, art. 145 (3).

20. *Supra note 5.*
21. *Original jurisdiction of the Supreme Court. Subject to the provisions of this Constitution, the Supreme Court shall, to the exclusion of any other court, have original jurisdiction in any dispute: (a) Between the Government of India and one or more States; (b) between the Government of India and any State or States on one side and one or more other States on the other; or (c) between two or more States, if and in so far as the dispute involves any question (whether of law or fact) on which the existence or extent of a legal right depends: Provided that the said jurisdiction shall not extend to a dispute arising out of any treaty, agreement, covenant, engagement, named or other similar instrument which, having been entered into or executed before the commencement of this Constitution, continues in operation after such commencement, or which provides that the said jurisdiction shall not extend to such a dispute. Constitution of India, art. 131. Note: The Constitution (Seventh Amendment) Act, 1956, it was substituted due to the absence of Part B states the clause in this article needs to be amended. It discusses the Supreme Court's original jurisdiction. The jurisdiction of the Supreme Court needs to be revised because the Part B states have changed.*
22. *Supra note 4.*
23. *Supra note 13.*
24. *Supra note 1.*